

RADiation harvesting of bioactive peptides from egg pr**O**-teins and their integration in ad**V**anced functional products

INNOVATION ACTION OF HORIZON EUROPE EURATOM RESEARCH AND TRAINING PROGRAMME GA N° 101061694

DELIVERABLE REPORT

Data Management Plan

DELIVERABLE: D5.5

Document identifier:	RADOV-Del-D5.5
Due date of deliverable:	End of month 6 (February 2023)
Report release date:	21/02/2023
Work package:	WP5 [Data Management Plan]
Lead beneficiary:	HUD
Document status:	Final

ABSTRACT

This deliverable explains the RADOV Data Management Plan. It describes the data the project will produce, where they come from, how they will be used and how these will be stored in Zenodo. This tool was designed to meet the EU Open Data requirements and our use of it, explained here, will ensure we also meet these requirements.

Funded by
the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Training programme under Grant Agreement No 101061694.

RADOV began in September 2022 and will run for 4 years.

Delivery Slip

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Edited by	Rob Edgecock	HUD	21/02/2023
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Approved by	Dagmara Chmielewska-Śmietanko	INCT	21/02/2023

Change Log

Version	Date	Amended by	Changes
v.1.0	27/01/2023	HUD	First draft
v.2.0	21/02/2023	INCT	Final formatting

Version Management

Reviewed by	All Partners
Approved by	All Partners
Authorized by	Coordinator, Dagmara Chmielewska-Śmietanko

Project Number: 101061694

Project Acronym: RADOV

Project title: RADiation harvesting of bioactive peptides from egg prOteins and their integration in adVanced functional products

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

1. Data Summary

What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

The RADOV project aims to develop and demonstrate the use of ionising radiation for egg white based proteins/peptides in order to achieve bioactivity improvement and to demonstrate the potential of the technique in two pilot products.

To do this, the work packages (WPs) of the project will collect the following data:

- WP1: project management data (reports, minutes, agendas)
- WP2: results of experiments on proteins irradiation, including data on irradiation conditions and the evolution of effects at laboratory scale. A database on irradiation conditions and observed effects will be created for use in other WPs.
- WP3: data from the experimental campaigns to characterise the materials produced (physico-chemical, structural, morphological, mechanical and biological evaluation)
- WP4: data to elaborate the demonstration of the products in the laboratory and at pilot scale.

Within the project, experimental and observational data will be generated and stored to make it accessible to the rest of the project's partners. Apart from above mentioned experimental data also information such as the results of a literature review, publications, conference presentations will be gathered and stored.

The data will be both quantitative and qualitative in nature and will be analysed from a range of methodological perspectives for project development and scientific purposes.

What types and formats of data will the project generate/collect?

RADOV will produce many datasets during the lifetime of the project. Examples include raw data for mass spectra (intensity vs. mass-to-charge ratio), chromatogram (detector response vs. retention time) and electropherogram (detector response vs. migration time). These will be structured and the resulting data stored in spreadsheets, text, and presentation formats to make them easily accessible by third parties and researchers who want to further use them or reproduce the results obtained. Some raw data will be produced by specialised equipment requiring proprietary software to analyse. In these cases, the data will also be saved in other more accessible formats.

Will you re-use any existing data and how?

Some existing data may be used in the early stages of the project to benchmark the work being done and verify the analyses being undertaken.

What is the origin of the data?

Within the project, experimental and observational data will be generated and stored to make it accessible to the rest of the project's partners. This will mainly come from measurements of the samples produced using a variety of equipment. Apart from the above mentioned experimental data also information such as result of a literature review will be gathered and stored.

Data will include experimental protocols, instrumental records and graphs of the results of sample analysis and dosimetry reports.

Pre-existing data will come from previous experiments performed by the partners.

What is the expected size of the data?

The total size of the data is expected to be around 1-2 TB. The maximum individual file size is restricted to 50GB.

To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

The data generated within the project will be re-used mainly by the beneficiaries for undertaking the activities required to reach the project objectives. The use of the results, to which data are likely to constitute a fundamental part, is regulated by the Consortium Agreement.

In addition to the members of the RADOV consortium, the data will be useful to companies and organisations interested in exploiting the results obtained by RADOV and expanding them into new applications. It may also be useful to researchers of radiation technologies involved in the development of new areas of ionising radiation application and businesses interested in advanced materials development.

2. FAIR data

2. 1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Data from the project will be stored in the Zenodo repository, see

<https://about.zenodo.org/principles>

This was developed with Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe in mind and meets all the FAIR requirements, as shown by the link above. All entries in Zenodo have a title and a description and a search feature allows the data to be found using a keyword search of these. RADOV members are being required to save their data with descriptive titles and with descriptions that will allow them to be easily found.

In addition, Zenodo creates metadata and Digital Object Identifiers for publications and data stored there. All metadata are stored internally by Zenodo in JSON-format according to a defined [JSON schema](#). Metadata are exported in several standard formats such as MARCXML, Dublin Core, and DataCite Metadata Schema. Zenodo also automatically implements versioning and we will make appropriate use of this.

A RADOV repository has been created at:

<https://zenodo.org/communities/radov/?page=1&size=20>

To ensure that the data used in the project is easily findable, we will make every effort to include standard identification mechanisms in all our publications, source code and tutorials.

2.2. Making data openly accessible

Due to the nature of this project, much of the data will be of commercial value as well as academic value. As a result, these data will have restricted access for a certain period of time, though every effort will be made to minimise this time period. Data of scientific value will be restricted until one month after publication. This will allow consortium members the time to analyse the data and publish the results and protect any results of commercial value. During this time, a summary of the data will be available on the project website.

In Zenodo, files may be deposited under closed, open, or embargoed access. Files deposited under closed access are protected against unauthorized access at all levels. Access to metadata and data files is provided over standard protocols such as HTTP and OAI-PMH. Data deposited under an embargo status require an end date for the embargo. The repository will restrict access to the data until the end of the embargo period; at which time, the content will become publicly available automatically. Users may deposit restricted files with the ability to share access with others if certain requirements are met. These files will not be made publicly available and sharing will be made possible only by the approval of depositor of the original file. To implement our data policy, RADOV will use open, embargoed and restricted access, but will endeavour to make all data open access as quickly as possible.

[How will the data be made accessible \(e.g. by deposition in a repository\)?](#)

The data will be made accessible by storage in the RADOV Zenodo repository. This will allow access to be restricted for the required period, but then moved to open access when this is completed.

[What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?](#)

The data will be structured and stored in pdf, spreadsheets, text, and presentation formats to allow easy access by third parties and researchers who want to further use the data or reproduce results produced.

[Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included?](#)

The data formats will be widely used standards and compliant with available software applications. No specialised software will be required.

2.3. Making data interoperable

The degree of interoperability of the data generated is expected to be high as common formats of files and metadata recognized standards will be used. The data will be structured and described in such a way as enables easy re-use. English language will be used for all published and internally shared data, considering the international composition of the consortium. If languages other than English are used, English transcripts/translations will be made available. Should any software product be developed and published as open data, a clear identification of the requirements for use will be provided.

2.4. Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)

Within RADOV project it is planned to make available for re-use:

- The project reports classified as Public in open access format
- Results published in open access format,
- The data supporting the papers.

As already described, access to data of scientific value will be restricted until one month after the publication of the papers. Access to data of commercial value will be restricted until the appropriate protection is in place, for example patents. However, the long-term goal of RADOV is to make all data open access. It is hoped that this can be done before the end of the project, but if the process takes longer, it may be necessary to extend this deadline.

The data will be available in Zenodo for as long as this exists. Currently, this is expected to be for at least another 20 years.

3. Allocation of resources

The use of Zenodo is free of charge for data and publications both during the project and after it is complete. A small budget for scientific paper publications has been set aside and RADOV will use existing agreements between partners and publishers for Gold Channel publications. Data management is the responsibility of WP5 and this will ensure that all partners in RADOV are meeting the requirements described in this DMP. However, while all activities encompassing any transfer of knowledge outside of the Consortium will be coordinated by the WP Leader, specific actions will be executed by designated partners publicising the project around Europe.

The DMP will be updated according to the schedule of deliverables set within the Grant Agreement

4. Data security

All data stored in Zenodo is backed up daily, so all partners will be encouraged to store their data there as soon as possible. Zenodo also assures the security of the data and allows it to be shared in a controlled manner.

Data not stored in Zenodo will be the responsibility of the partner who generates it for ensuring they are regularly backed up and stored securely according to internal safe keeping procedures. If such data is also shared internally in the Consortium, the data owner will be responsible also for the methods used to share information.

5. Ethical aspects

There are no expected ethical or legal issues with our data sharing and we are not expecting to store any personal data.

6. Other issues

There are no other issues.